

Optimizing Accessibility to Polling Stations: A Spatial Equity Approach

Using Population-Weighted Voronoi Analysis

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Introduction

Inclusive democratic participation requires equitable access to polling stations, a challenge especially for voters with disabilities. This study presents a geospatial framework to optimize the placement of Accessible Polling Stations (APS) using population-weighted Voronoi analysis in four Israeli cities: Jerusalem, Tel Aviv, Haifa, and Beer Sheva. By integrating demographic data into Voronoi-generated service areas, we assess spatial equity through deviations between actual coverage and ideal zones inversely proportional to population density. The optimization process iteratively adjusts APS locations using adaptive corrections scaled by an exponential decay function, gradually aligning service areas with population distribution and reducing access disparities.

City	Population	Area (ha)	Density	Number of PA	Number of APS	APS Score
Be'er Sheva	214164	10098	21	47	31 (70%)	0.51
Jerusalem	981715	10750	91	152	74 (49%)	0.17
Tel Aviv	474533	4437	107	97	78 (80%)	0.53
Haifa	290305	4321	67	73	46 (63%)	0.53

Example - Be'er Sheva

